

1. Head of the planthopper, showing the characteristic vertical bands.

2. Head of the BPH.

The head of the planthopper shows vertical black bands on the frons (Fig. 1). These appear to be its characteristic feature, and are not seen in BPH (Fig. 2). The ventral side of the abdomen in the 4th- and 5th-instar nymphs shows a pair of distinct black spots laterally on either side near the 5th segment.

Specimens have been identified as *Toya* spp. by CAB International Institute of Entomology, London.

Although ricefields adjacent to the Sewage Farm were not infested with this planthopper, adult females caged after 5 h of starvation on 40-d-old IR50 rice seedlings were found to thrive for the next 56 h.

Usually, the planthopper moves more swiftly than BPH, but becomes less active after a starvation period. Insects

regain their natural poise after a few hours on rice plants, indicating possible force-feeding. Actual feeding experiments on rice seedlings showed a mean weight of 7.0 mg honeydew/adult as against 22.7 mg on the regular host.

No survival occurred among 40 freshly hatched nymphs confined on 35-d-old IR50 rice seedlings.

After 56 h on rice plants, the insects had oviposited an average 26 eggs/ insect, in batches of 6-9 eggs. □

Chemical control of thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* in the rice nursery

V. V. Madhusudhan and M. Gopalan,
Agricultural Entomology Department,
Centre for Plant Protection Studies, Tamil
Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore
641003, India

Spray formulations of phosphamidon, monocrotophos, phosalone, chlorpyrifos, metasystox, endosulfan, dimethoate, and neem oil were evaluated for control of rice thrips in the rice nursery. The field experiment with nine treatments including control was

laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Pregerminated seeds of IR20 were sown in 0.5-m² plots. Thrips infestation was noticed 10 d after sowing and pretreatment counts were taken on 15 randomly selected seedlings. Counts were taken at 24, 48, and 72 h, and 1 wk, and 2 wk after treatment.

All chemicals were significantly effective in controlling thrips (see table). Chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, and monocrotophos were best. Although neem oil did not reduce thrips population significantly 24 h after application, it did reduce population at 48 and 72 h after application. □

Effect of insecticides for thrips control.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Population ^b (no.)						
	Pretreatment	24 h	48 h	72 h	1 wk	2 wk	Mean
Phosalone (0.07%)	5.9	0.2 ab	0.9 ab	0.4 a	1.4 b	4.5 d	1.7 b
Chlorpyrifos (0.04%)	5.1	1.1 ab	0.9 b	0.7 abc	0.7 a	1.2 a	0.9 a
Monocrotophos (0.04%)	6.6	0.9 a	0.3 a	0.4 a	1.5 b	3.1 c	1.2 a
Metasystox (0.04%)	6.9	1.7 b	0.6 ab	0.5 ab	1.8 b	3.4 c	1.6 b
Dimethoate (0.04%)	5.2	1.2 ab	0.6 ab	0.5 a	0.6 a	1.9 b	0.9 a
Phosphamidon (0.04%)	5.4	1.7 b	0.9 b	0.9 abc	0.9 abc	3.6 c	1.8 b
Endosulfan (0.05%)	5.4	2.5 c	1.6 c	1.0 c	1.9 c	4.8 d	2.4 c
Neem oil (2.0%)	5.7	4.9 d	1.8 c	1.4 d	2.3 c	4.3 d	2.9 d
Control	5.7	4.8 d	5.8 d	6.4 e	7.6 d	7.8 e	6.5 e
Period mean		2.2 b	1.5 a	1.4 a	2.2 b	3.8 c	

^aMean of 45 seedlings. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level. In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level.

Alternate ricefield hosts of the Angoumois grain moth

A. Dakshinamurthy and A. Regupathy,
Entomology Department, Tamil Nadu
Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003,
India

The Angoumois grain moth *Sitotroga cerealella* is an important pest of rice,

wheat, barley, millet, and maize. Field infestation is carried to storage, where it causes severe losses in quality and quantity.

Field infestation on different hosts can identify source of inoculum for rice and other cereals. In places where rice is grown in a particular season, the pest may survive on alternate hosts in other seasons to reinfest the next rice crop.